

A Deep Learning based Ensemble Model for Generalized Mitosis detection in H&E stained Whole Slide Images

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ABSTRACT

Identification of mitotic cells as well as estimation of mitotic index are important parameters in understanding the pathology of cancer, predicting response to chemotherapy and overall survival. Currently, this process is commonly done manually by people trained in pathology. However, there appears to be a significant variability in the assessments. The uses of deep learning models could help in addressing this issue. Some of the state-of-the-art methods available are trained for specific cancer types and often tend to fail when used across multiple tumor types. Hence the need for a more 'pan-tumor' approach to identifying mitotic figures.

In this work, we built a generalized deep learning ensemble model for mitosis detection and classification models using the MIDOG-2022 Challenge datasets. Our model is able to generalize well to unseen tumor tissue types, instrument variability and lab variability. Our approach achieved a F1-score of 0.7704 on the preliminary test set.

1 INTRODUCTION

Mitosis is the process of the cell cycle wherein cells divide into two daughter cells enabling growth and replacement of cells. In cancer, there is a loss of normal cell cycle control resulting in increased mitosis resulting in uncontrolled cancer cell proliferation as well as genomic instability. Identification of mitotic figures is thus an important aspect in histopathological analyses of cancer done on whole slide images (WSIs).

The most common method of identification of mitotic cells is manual examination of hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) stained tissue slides. With advances in the field of computational or digital pathology [Dawson, 2022], there have been developments in building highly advanced scanners to capture images from H&E-stained whole slides. However, many state-of-the-art methods are trained on whole slide images of any one tumor tissue type and hence tend to drop in precision when used on other tumor type WSIs. The inter-lab differences in staining outcome as well as differences in scanner

outputs have also affected the precision and recall of many digital pathology methods. Hence there is still a lack of adoption of computer-based tools by clinical pathologists [Jiménez and Racoceanu, 2019].

There have been a number of attempts to help address the issues encountered in the use of digital pathology in the analysis of histopathological images. Specific to mitosis, there have been many Challenges organized such as TUPAC16 [Veta et al, 2019], Mitos & Atypia 14 [Mitos & Atypia 14 Contest 2014], and MIDOG-2021 [Aubreville M et al, 2022 (a)]. In the MIDOG 2021 challenge [Aubreville M et al, 2022 (a)], the aim was to look at methods to help overcome the domain shift caused by using a multiple scanner. Human breast cancer histopathology images were used in this challenge.

In the MIDOG 2022 challenge [Aubreville M et al, 2022 (b)], the goal is to develop and analyze approaches that help resolve the problem of domain-shift across tissues. Such approaches should try to enhance the performance of deep learning methods when applied to mitotic figure detection from H&E stained WSIs across different tumor types. The approach would ideally address differences caused by various cell features including size and shape, multiple scanner specifications, tissue preparation differences as well as staining differences across multiple laboratories. We propose a deep learning based ensemble model that detects mitotic figures and then classifies the detected mitotic figures for better generalization and accuracy.

2 MATERIALS & METHODS

The proposed approach has the following steps - data pre-processing and building an ensemble model.

2.1 Data

The MIDOG 2022 microscopy domain generalization challenge organizers have provided the participants

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with a training set of digitized microscopy slides prepared from different tumor cases. These were obtained from a few laboratories and from different scanners. The scanners included in this study are 3DHitech Panoramic Scan II, Aperio ScanScope CS2, Hamamatsu S360, Hamamatsu NanoZoomer XR and Leica GT450. The training set consisted of 6 tumor types from human and dog. These were scanned using different whole slide scanners mentioned earlier, so as to capture as much of variability as possible. This dataset consisted of 150 human breast cancer cases (obtained from the MIDOG 2021 challenge), 44 canine lung cancer cases, 55 canine lymphomas, 55 human neuroendocrine tumors, 50 canine cutaneous mast cell tumors, and 49 human melanoma cases - a total of 403 cases. The human melanoma images were not labelled. There were also 2 duplicate cases, which were removed. The preliminary test set provided for algorithm validation contained 5 cases each of 4 different tumor types which will not be part of the final test set. The final test set will contain 10 cases each of 10 other tumor types which are unknown to the participants, and these tumor types are not from those seen during training.

2.2 Data pre-processing

Based on the 354 labeled images in the dataset, training and validation datasets are created using 80:20 split. The MIDOG 2022 dataset is biased towards non-mitotic figures over mitotic figures. To overcome this bias and avoid overfitting, we performed augmentation and oversampling of mitotic patches. First, 512x512 pixel contextual regions around the mitotic/imposter figures are extracted by applying random shift to the context window from each WSI. Second, for each annotated patch, we generate contextual regions in the ratio 2:1 for mitotic and non-mitotic patches respectively. We randomly pick equal number of mitotic and non-mitotic patches from these contextual and annotated regions. Standard augmentation methods such as horizontal flipping, vertical flipping, random rescaling, random cropping, and random rotation are performed to make the model invariant to geometric perturbations across different tissue types. Furthermore, Random HSV is also applied to randomly change the hue, saturation, and value of images in the hue saturation value (HSV) color space for making the model robust to color perturbations caused by variability in scanners and batch effects. Additionally, equal number of mitotic and non-mitotic patches of size 96x96 pixels from annotated and contextual regions were also separately extracted in a similar fashion. The above augmentations were applied to these patches as well.

2.3 Building an ensemble model

Our ensemble model involves performing (a) detection of mitotic and non-mitotic from the 512x512 patches and (b) a separate classification model that is applied to the detected mitotic and non-mitotic figures. The final class probability is obtained by aggregating the prediction scores from these two models.

Mitosis Detection Model: Detection Transformer (DETR) [Carion et al, 2020] with Resnet50-DC5 backbone pretrained on ImageNet, Adam optimizer with initial learning rate of 1e-03 is trained on the dataset of 512x512 regions with 80:20 split for detection of mitotic and non-mitotic figures. The optimized hyperparameters for the model are obtained using Optuna hyperparameter optimization framework [Akiba et al, 2019]. This trained DETR model achieved F1 score of 0.804 on the validation dataset.

Mitosis Classification Model: EfficientNet-B7 [Tan and Le, 2019] pretrained on ImageNet, Adam optimizer with initial learning rate of 1e-03 and with binary cross entropy as the loss is trained on the dataset of 96x96 mitotic and non-mitotic patches with a 80:20 split. The hyperparameters of the EfficientNet-B7 are chosen using Optuna hyperparameter optimization framework. This trained EfficientNet-B7 model achieved F1 score of 0.84 on the validation dataset.

Ensemble Model: For the test WSI images, using a sliding window with overlay of 50 pixels, cropped regions of size 512x512 pixels are extracted. Each cropped region is first fed to the trained DETR model. The DETR output consists of the identified objects and their associated class probabilities. All mitotic predictions with high class probability greater than or equal to 0.9 are directly included in the final output with the mitotic class label. We extract 96x96 regions for the remaining predictions and pass these to the classification model described above. The final class probabilities for these objects are obtained by aggregating the DETR and classifier prediction probabilities. Aggregate mitotic probabilities greater than or equal to the threshold of 0.75 are included in the final output with mitotic class label.

We also use patches from the unlabeled tumor tissue for training the classifier. For this, the high confidence DETR predictions with class probabilities above 0.9 are considered as pseudo labels for training the tissue. A total of 5317 patches comprising 1022 mitotic and 4295 non-mitotic patches are included in the training set. An equal number of mitotic and non-mitotic patches are selected from these 5317 patches and their corresponding contextual regions. Training dataset is created using the four labelled tumor types (human breast cancer, canine lung, lymphoma and mast cell) and one unlabeled

tumor type (human melanoma). The validation dataset is created from the human neuroendocrine tumor tissue type. The classifier is trained on this training dataset and evaluated on validation dataset to assess the performance on the unseen tissue types. However, no significant improvement in the performance is observed in terms of F1-score on the validation dataset after including the unlabeled tumor tissue types.

For the preliminary test set and the final test phase, we train the mitosis detector and classifier models on the entire labelled training data of 354 images. The models are implemented using Pytorch framework and all experiments are run on Nvidia DGX A100.

3 RESULTS

Table 1 shows the performance using F1 score of our approach and the baselines provided by the organizers on the preliminary test set across four tumor types and on the validation set. Our model outperforms the Challenge baselines and is able to generalize well across the tumor tissue types provided in the preliminary test set.

Table 1. F1 score for this model on Challenge data

Model	F1 (Validation set)	F1 (Preliminary test set)				
		Total	T1	T2	T3	T4
Our Model	0.809	0.770	0.790	0.792	0.720	0.831
Baseline 2	-	0.715	0.744	0.732	0.692	0.711
Baseline 1	-	0.629	0.753	0.608	0.585	0.743

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